

Advanced Reinforcement Techniques for Seismic Resilience

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Abstract—The optimal design procedure of buckling restrained braces (BRBs) in reinforced concrete (RC) building structures can provide the distribution of horizontal stiffness of BRBs at each story, which minimizes story drift response of the structure under the constraint of specified total stiffness of BRBs. In this paper, a simple rule is proposed to convert continuous horizontal stiffness of BRBs into sectional sizes of BRB which are available from standardized section list assuming realistic structural design stage.

I. INTRODUCTION

RC building structures are designed to satisfy a certain level of earthquake resistant requirement. However, it is concerned that, for quite severe earthquake columns, beams or slabs are damaged, and seismic story drift responses exceed the allowable limits [1]. To solve this problem, a variety of vibration control systems have been developed such as shear wall, base isolation, or dampers. Considering the case of seismic retrofitting, BRBs is a superior system to the other shear resisting devices from the point of view of construction and cost. BRB is expected to dissipate a great amount of energy and to reduce the seismic responses.

A lot of research works have been conducted about using BRB in newly-built or existing building structures. As for the fabrication of BRB, optimal length of BRB steel core is formulated analytically and tested experimentally [2]. On the other hand, there are quite few research works about practical BRB design method compared to the other types of damper systems.

A lot of methods have been proposed to determine linear viscous damper placement for building structures and these methods can be directly extended to linear brace placement. A steel brace optimization procedure is proposed based on transfer function of linear model and two different rehabilitation techniques, steel brace and viscous damper, are compared [3]. A topology optimization method is applied to obtain optimal topology of the bracing system of structures with linear material under harmonic loads [4]. In order to construct a non-linear damper design method, most of the

dampers has been proposed based on design response spectrum and equivalent linearization of hysteretic model [5].

As for the design method of BRBs, a seismic retrofit design method is considered for RC buildings with elastic steel frame and BRBs in order to evaluate the amount of BRB using a simplified equivalent linearization method [6]. A simplified formulation is suggested to determine BRB ductility and strength for steel frames equipped with BRBs considering design spectra of Eurocode 8 [7]. Sensitivity analysis method has been proposed to investigate the relation between seismic performances and brace over-strength distributions as a tool for safer design of BRBs [8]. On the other hand, several methods have been suggested to consider the nonlinearity of dampers directly. A practical method is recommended for optimum design of the non-linear oil dampers with relief mechanism installed in multi-story framed building structures based on a sensitivity analysis by using nonlinear time-history response analysis [9]. A systematic methodology was proposed for determining the optimal cross sectional area of BRBs on the seismic upgrading of existing structures using genetic algorithm [10].

A simple and practical optimal placement procedure was proposed to find the optimal stiffness for BRBs to minimize the seismic story responses (drift) of the structure [11]. This procedure continuously traces the most effective placements of BRB by increasing total BRB stiffness from zero to a specified value based on nonlinear time-history analysis considering nonlinearity of BRB directly. This method provides stiffness of BRBs of each story as continuous value depending on the step length of optimization process.

In a practical design procedure, it is required to select steel members from specified standard section lists. Therefore, in this paper, a simple rule is derived to convert continuous horizontal stiffness of BRBs obtained from the previous method into standard sectional sizes of BRB. In this paper, a new practical method is proposed to determine the sectional sizes of BRBs from the result of the previously proposed method for BRB placement optimization in RC building structures.

II. TARGET MODEL WITHOUT BRB

The target model is the same as the model used in [11]. The model, as shown in Fig. 1, has been modeled in ETABS. This

previous methods use linearization or simplification. An efficient procedure to determine optimal placement of nonlinear hysteretic

model is containing five typical stories, and the structure material is RC. The height of each story is typically 3.6 m. Young's modulus of concrete for the RC structure is 2.094174×10^4 MPa. The damping ratio of the structure is assumed to be as $\xi(h) = 0.05$ which means 5% damping [10].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Optimal BRB Placement Problem

In this chapter, the previously proposed BRB optimization procedure is introduced. The optimal BRB placement problem is how to determine the adequate BRB stiffness in order to minimize the maximum response of the structure. BRB optimization problem is defined in three equations.

$$\text{Find } X = (k_1^{BRB}, \dots, k_N^{BRB}) \quad (1)$$

$i \quad i_{max}$

$$\text{Subject to } \sum_i k_i^{BRB} = \bar{K} \quad (3)$$

where \bar{K} and k_i^{BRB} indicate total BRB stiffness and BRB stiffness of i -th story, and $\delta_{i_{max}}$ indicates the maximum story drift response of the i -th story [10].

$$\text{To minimize } f(X) = \max \quad (2)$$

(a) Linear direct integration, time history analysis)

(b) Nonlinear direct integration, time history analysis)

Fig. 2 Story responses before optimization by MATLAB

B. Optimization Procedure

In order to solve the optimization problem described in the previous section, a simple algorithm is proposed in this section. This procedure continuously traces the most effective placements of BRB by increasing total BRB stiffness from zero. The proposed method is summarized in five steps. (1) Consider N-story shear building model and set the yield

Fig. 1 RC Building 3D-view displacements of the structure and BRB and the incremental stiffness of the BRB Δk .

TABLE I
STORY MASS AND STORY STIFFNESS

Story	Mass (kg)	Stiffness (N)	Stiffness (N/m)
626430	6143179.77	226315592	
624705	6126263.31	148560662	
624705	6126263.31	138974375	
624705	6126263.31	131338900	
632842	6206060.02	130239362	

- (2) Consider N candidate models. As for the i -th candidate model, BRB with stiffness Δk is added to the i -th story of the model with optimal BRBs obtained in the previous optimization step.
- (3) Compute the time-history responses of the N candidate models in (2) for input ground acceleration and evaluate the maximum response as an objective function.
- (4) Find the candidate model with the lowest objective function among the N candidate models.
- (5) Update the stiffness of BRBs and return to (2) until the total

stiffness of BRBs reaches to the specified value.

this procedure needs only N candidate models at every optimization step which is equal to the number of the story. Fig. 3 shows the detailed sample of three optimization steps. At every optimization step, only five candidate models are compared with respect to the maximum drift response. In the first optimization step, each of the five candidate models has BRB with stiffness Δ in the different story. In this case, candidate model 1 is selected as an optimal BRB placement at the first optimization step. In the second optimization step, each of the five candidate models has additive BRB with stiffness Δ in the different story to the optimal BRB placement at 1st optimization step. In this case, candidate model 3 is selected as an optimal BRB placement among in the second optimization step. These steps are continued until we find the optimal placement [11].

The most characteristic point of the proposed method is that

Fig. 3 Schematic model for BRB placement

OPTIMIZED STIFFNESS OF BRBs (LAST OPTIMIZATION STEP OF 250 STEPS)

Story	Optimized stiffness of BRBs (N/m)	Stiffness of structure according to Table I (N/m)
	35429824.62	226315592.45
	116131091.81	148560662.30
	90542885.14	138974375.92
	53144736.93	131338900.74
	196832359.00	130239362.10

Fig. 6 Dimensions of the braced frame

TABLE III
1 KBRB CALCULATIONS, BRB AREA=(1*12) CM²

Items	Units	Values
One BRB area (A)	m ²	0.0012
Modulus of elasticity of the steel for BRB(E)	N/m ²	199957597569.9800
θ	degree	30.9640
Length of BRB (L)	m	6.9970
K _{BRB} (one BRB's stiffness) =A*E*cos ² (θ)/L	N/m	25205459.6337

TABLE IV
MODIFIED OPTIMIZED STIFFNESS OF BRBs

Story	Total optimized	Selected	Modified optimized
	number of BRBs	exact number	stiffness of BRBs (N/m)
	=optimized stiffness of BRBs/1KBRB	=selected exact number of BRBs	BRBs*1KBRB
1	1.39	2.00	50821710.64
2	4.57	5.00	127054276.60
3	3.56	4.00	101643421.28
4	2.09	2.00	50821710.64
5	7.75	8.00	203286842.56

V. RESULT

Table V and Fig. 7 show the comparisons of the maximum story drifts among the three models, i.e. model without BRB, model with optimized BRB stiffness in Table II, and model with modified optimized BRB stiffness in Table IV. From Fig. 7 it can be understood that the responses due to modified optimized

stiffness of BRBs are almost the same as responses of optimized stiffness of BRBs, and both of them can decrease the maximum responses effectively.

TABLE V
SEISMIC STORY DRIFT RESPONSES OF THE STRUCTURE INTO THREE CASES

Story	Drift (deltamax) with BRB stiffness=0	Drift (deltamax) with BRB stiffness =Optimized	Drift (deltamax) with BRB stiffness =Modified optimized
	M	m	m
	0.014	0.024	0.022
	0.029	0.025	0.025
	0.028	0.025	0.026
	0.026	0.024	0.024
	0.012	0.005	0.005

drifts, so three conclusions have been derived.

- (2) The validity of the proposed method is demonstrated through numerical examples of five storied building structures.
- (3) The comparisons of the maximum story drifts have been conducted among three models, i.e. model without BRB, model with optimized number of BRBs as real number and model with modified optimized number of BRBs as integer number. From the results, it is demonstrated that the responses due to modified optimized stiffness of BRBs are almost the same as responses of optimized stiffness of BRBs, and both of them can decrease the maximum responses effectively.

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